

Multiscale forming simulation of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics: an application of supercomputer

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Background

Forming Process of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTPs) have drawn increasing attentions from both academia and industry owing to its unique advantage of highly efficient production compared to thermosetting composite

High Performance Thermoplastics Market Size, by Region, 2015-2026 (USD Billion)

Quoted: IHI, technical report

Commercial Forecast of High-Performance Thermoplastic Composites

Target Manufacture CFRTP with better quality

Challenges

- Complex forming process
- Complex geometric shape & layout
- Deformation, Residual Stress

Solution

- Finite Element Analysis
- Heat transfer analysis
- Strain analysis
- Viscoelastic analysis

1 Background

Key issues in the Forming Process Simulation

- Multiscale temperature/time-dependent material properties

- Modeling of three-dimensional (3D) thermo-viscoelastic material

- Temperature gradient & Tool-Part Interaction

There are three key issues in the forming process simulation of CFRTP.

Quoted:

Composite Structures, 2015, 129: 60-69.

Materials, 2018, 11: 464(1-18).

Materials, 2020, 13(20): 1-13.

1 Background

Multiscale Simulation of the Forming Process

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Background

FrontCOMP

Massively parallel computing

Experiment verification

1 Background

Simulation of long fiber composite

Using shear lag principle to extract useful information

A large three-dimensional model of randomly distributed long fiber was established and solved, and the statistical distribution of the residual stress was given

Normal stress distribution

Stress within fiber and resin

Relation between inter-fiber spacing & stress

1 Background

Simulation of short fiber composite

Thermal stress

Stress under mechanical loading

Large-scale finite element analysis of short fiber composites yields the statistical distribution of Burr function under thermal/mechanical loading, which explains the influence of microscopic stress on material strength

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AH Method Implementation

3.1 Forming Process and Two-Step Homogenization

GF/PEI woven fabric composites

GF/PEI woven fabric composites

Two-Step Homogenization

UD-RVE and WF-RVE

FE model of the WF-RVE

Homogenization of thermal conductivity:
Node Number: 137949;
Element type: DC3D4.

Homogenization of viscoelastic & CTE:
Nodes number: 90510.
Element type: C3D4;

Two-step homogenization of woven fabric (WF) structure is developed using new strategy

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AH Method Implementation

3.2 AH Implementation for Unsteady-State Thermal Conduction

Analytical Homogenization of Effective Density and Specific Heat Capacity:

$$V_f(T) = \frac{M_f / \rho_f(T)}{M_f / \rho_f(T) + M_{resin} / \rho_{resin}(T)} \quad (a)$$

$$\rho^h(T) = \rho_{warp}(T)V_{warp}(T) + \rho_{weft}(T)V_{weft}(T) + \rho_m(T)V_m(T) \quad (b)$$

$$Cp^h(T) = Cp_{warp}(T)M_{warp}(T) + Cp_{weft}(T)M_{weft}(T) + Cp_m(T)M_m(T) \quad (c)$$

Effective Thermal Conduction Tensor:

$$k_{ij}^h = \left\langle k_{ij}(\mathbf{y}, T^\epsilon) \left[\mathbf{IH}(t) - \frac{\partial \chi^i(\mathbf{y}, T^\epsilon, t)}{\partial y_i} \right] \right\rangle_{\mathbf{y}} \quad (d)$$

Temperature-dependent

In contrast to the conventional AH method, the new space-time AH method can model temperature-dependency during the AH homogenization.

AH of thermal properties

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AH Method Implementation

3.3 AH Implementation for Linear Viscoelasticity

New Time-domain AH method

Integral Form Equation of Characteristic Displacement

Tensor:

$$u_i^{(1)}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, t) = -\frac{\partial \chi_i^{kl}(\mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial t} * \frac{\partial u_k^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_l}$$

$$\int_Y C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, t) * \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial \chi_k^{mn}(\mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial y_l} \frac{\partial v_i(t)}{\partial y_j} dy = \int_Y \frac{\partial C_{ijmn}(\mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial y_j} v_i(t) dy$$

Effective Constitutive Equation:

$$\langle \sigma_{ij}^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t) \rangle_Y = C_{ijmn}^h(t) * \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial u_m^{(0)}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial x_n}$$

Effective Relaxation Tensor:

$$C_{ijmn}^H(t) = \left\langle C_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}, t) * \left[I_{klmn} \delta(t) - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial \chi_k^{mn}(\mathbf{y}, t)}{\partial y_l} \right] \right\rangle_Y$$

Time-Temperature Superposition Principle:

$$C_{ijkl}^h(T, \tau) = C_{ijkl}^h\left(T_0, \frac{\tau}{a_T^m}\right) = C_{ijkl}^h(T_0, t)$$

One integral form characteristic displacement tensor

Straightforward

Time- and temperature-dependent effective relaxation tensor

Characteristic Displacement Tensor:

Characteristic displacement tensor components of the woven fabric composite

The AH method can compute time-dependent characteristic displacement tensors and the effective relaxation tensor straightforwardly, and do not need Laplace transform.

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AH Method Implementation

3.3 AH Implementation for Linear Viscoelasticity

Master Curves (@ 160 °C)

Master Curves of Effective relaxation stiffness at 160 °C

Shifted Relaxation Stiffness (from 160 to 220 °C)

Relaxation Curves of Effective relaxation stiffness at 220 °C

Shifted Relaxation Stiffness (from 160 to 240 °C)

Relaxation Curves of Effective relaxation stiffness at 240 °C

The UMAT subroutine is efficient in modeling a 3D anisotropic viscoelastic material, and the computation results are accurate. Therefore, the shortage of modeling 3D viscoelasticity in the ABAQUS is fixed.

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AH Method Implementation

3.4 AH Implementation for Thermal Expansion Coefficient

Mechanical Characteristic Displacement Tensor:

Reference Temperature = 50 °C, Deformation scale = 100.

Mechanical characteristic displacement tensor in normal directions

Thermal Stress Characteristic Displacement Tensor:

Reference Temperature = 50 °C, Deformation scale = 500.

Thermal stress characteristic displacement tensor

Reference Temperature = 50 °C, Deformation scale = 500.

Mechanical characteristic displacement tensor in shear directions

Effective CTE:

Temperature-dependent effective thermal expansion coefficient

Results in Figs. 36-39 indicate that the AH implementation method is efficient to compute mechanical and thermal stress characteristic temperature tensors, as well as the temperature-dependent CTE.

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Research on the Forming Process of GF/PEI Laminate

4.1 Thermoforming Experiment

Forming Experiment of the GF/PEI Woven Fabric Composite

Macroscale

Mesoscale

- (1) The unbalanced temperature gradient causes warpage during the forming process.
- (2) There are no voids in the GF/PEI woven fabric composites in the mesoscale.

4 Research on the Forming Process of GF/PEI Laminate

4.2 Forming Simulation

Forming Simulation and Residual Deformation

Shear Layer Model

Analytical Solution for Shear Stress:

$$\tau = \frac{G_A (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) \Delta T \sinh(\lambda x)}{t_A \cdot \lambda \cosh(\lambda L)}$$

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{G_A (E_1 h_1 + E_2 h_2)}{t_A E_1 h_1 \cdot E_2 h_2}}$$

τ : Shear stress; G : Shear Modulus; ΔT : temperature change;
 t_A : Shear layer thickness; h : height; α : CTE;
 subscript 1 and 2 represents composite and mold.

Employment of the shear layer can model the shear stress induced by the mismatch of CTE between mold and composite, and the most reasonable shear layer modulus is 5 MPa.

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Research on the Forming Process of GF/PEI Laminate

4.2 Forming Simulation

Discussion of the Temperature and Strain

Monitoring section and path in the finite element model

Temperature change during the thermoforming process

Thermal strain and thermal strain rate during the forming process

Actual strain and actual strain rate during the forming process

The forming process can be divided into 5 stages based on the temperature profiles.

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Research on the Forming Process of GF/PEI Wing Leading Edge

5.1 Multi-Step Thermoforming Experiment

Two-Step Fabrication Experiment of Wing Leading Edge

Molds for the wing leading edge

Temperature and pressure profiles during the thermoforming process

Mold, Temperature and Pressure

Multi-step thermoforming process

3D Scan Method

Residual Deformation

A two-step forming process is efficient to fabricate a GF/PEI composite wing leading edge.

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Research on the Forming Process of GF/PEI Wing Leading Edge

5.2 Forming Simulation

Forming Simulation

Temperature loads in the forming simulation

Temperature and pressure profiles during the thermoforming process

Temperature Gradient and Residual Displacement

Temperature contour during the forming process

Residual deformation (a) with shear layer (b) without shear layer

Simulation result obtained by the shear layer is more accurate than the simulation result obtained by the finite element model without the shear layer.

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Research on the Forming Process of GF/PEI Wing Leading Edge

5.2 Forming Simulation

Stress Analysis:

Stress changes before and after demolding (with a shear layer)

Stress change before and after demolding (without shear layer)

σ_{11} and σ_{22} are the in-plane stress and are more balanced, σ_{11} is chosen for further warpage analysis. σ_{33} is the out-of-plane stress and has a stress gradient because the pressure varies over the shape of the wing leading edge.

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- (1) Theoretical research on asymptotic homogenization for unsteady-state thermal conduction, linear viscoelasticity and thermal expansion in the thermo-viscoelastic composite is respectively studied and analytical methods for effective density, specific heat capacity, numerical implementation methods for effective thermal conductivity, linear viscoelasticity and thermal expansion coefficient are presented.
- (2) Creating unidirectional-RVE and woven fabric-RVE through experiment method, calculating effective material moduli of GF/PEI composite and investigating the temperature gradient influence on the stress, strain and residual deformation during the forming process through experimental validation and numerical simulation.
- (3) Proposing a multi-step forming technique to fabricate GF/PEI composite wing leading edge and simulating the forming process of a GF/PEI composite wing leading edge to study temperature gradient and tool-part impacts on the residual deformation, as well as the mechanism of warpage during the demolding process on the macroscale.

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Thank You!